

Potential of traditional and recirculation inland aquaculture for inclusive and intelligent fisheries development in the Baltic States (AQUA4DEV-BS)/1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/218

Version 1

Description

The project generates interdisciplinary data to analyse barriers and drivers of inland aquaculture and to develop a decision-support tool (DST) for stakeholders. Data include qualitative interviews, comparative legal and policy analysis, and structured modelling outputs.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027 (project 1.1.1.9/1/24/I/001)

"Post-doctoral Research")

Researchers

Leila Neimane (orcid:0000-0002-7905-0208)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Potential of traditional and recirculation inland aquaculture for inclusive and intelligent fisheries development in the Baltic States (AQUA4DEV-BS)/1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/218

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027 (project 1.1.1.9/1/24/I/001 "Post-doctoral Research")

Project: Potential of traditional and recirculation inland aquaculture for inclusive and intelligent fisheries development in the Baltic States (AQUA4DEV-BS) (No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/218)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Structured decision-support tool (DST)

This DMP is created within the AQUA4DEV-BS project to support the analysis of inland aquaculture development in the Baltic States. It contributes to identifying key barriers and drivers and to developing a structured decision-support tool (DST). The dataset forms part of the empirical and analytical basis of the project, enabling evidence-based conclusions and supporting both scientific outputs and practical applications for stakeholders.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data collection supports the main objective of the AQUA4DEV-BS project, which is to assess the potential of inland aquaculture in the Baltic States and to develop a decision-support tool (DST) for stakeholders. The data are used to identify key barriers and drivers of aquaculture development (RO1), to perform a comparative analysis of aquaculture systems (RO2), and to construct and validate structured decision pathways within the DST (RO3).

The project combines both primary and secondary data. Primary data are collected through semi-structured interviews with aquaculture stakeholders and experts, while secondary data include legal frameworks, policy documents, and case study materials from the Baltic States and selected comparative countries. The integration of these data sources enables a comprehensive, evidence-based

analysis and supports the development of practical and scientifically grounded outputs.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Coded documents
- Process produced data
- Other

Structured decision-support data (DST), including decision pathways, scenario models, and multi-criteria evaluation outputs

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- PNG
- XLS
- Others

NVivo project files (qualitative analysis), DOCX documents, and structured decision-support model files.

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100 - 300

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data generated and analysed in this project will be useful for multiple target groups. Researchers and academic institutions can use the data for further studies on aquaculture, environmental policy, and interdisciplinary governance. Policy-makers and public authorities can use the findings and structured outputs, including the decision-support tool (DST), to support evidence-based policy design and implementation. Aquaculture industry stakeholders, particularly micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), can use the results to inform investment decisions, production strategies, and adaptation to regulatory and market conditions. In addition, international organisations and the general public may benefit from improved knowledge and awareness of sustainable aquaculture development.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Data Package

As no single metadata standard fully covers all data types in this interdisciplinary project, a combination of structured and descriptive metadata will be created. For structured datasets, Data Package elements will be used, including descriptions of variables, formats, and data structure. For qualitative and textual data, metadata will include information on data origin, methodology (e.g. interview protocols, sampling), context, and processing steps (e.g. coding and analysis).

All datasets will be accompanied by clear documentation, including dataset descriptions, keywords, versioning, and methodological notes, ensuring that the data are understandable and reusable by other researchers and stakeholders.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Project-specific keyword naming convention

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Access to certain datasets will be restricted due to the presence of sensitive information, particularly qualitative data obtained through interviews with stakeholders (e.g. aquaculture SMEs and institutional representatives).

Legal and ethical reasons: The primary restriction relates to data protection and confidentiality requirements. Interview data may contain personal data and potentially sensitive business or policy-related information. In accordance with ethical standards and applicable data protection regulations (e.g. GDPR), such data will be anonymised and will not be publicly shared in raw form.

Voluntary restrictions: In addition, access to detailed qualitative data may be limited to protect the confidentiality of participants and to maintain trust with stakeholders involved in the research process.

Access arrangements: Aggregated and anonymised data, as well as structured outputs (e.g. comparative analyses and decision-support tool components), will be made openly available where possible. Access to more detailed datasets may be granted upon reasonable request for research purposes, subject to ethical considerations and data protection requirements. Where appropriate, controlled access procedures (e.g. data sharing agreements) will be applied.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv/>

The selected repositories, DataverseLV and Zenodo, are widely recognised platforms for research data management and are appropriate for the types of data generated in this project. DataverseLV provides a national infrastructure aligned with institutional practices in Latvia and is suitable for structured datasets, while Zenodo ensures international visibility, long-term preservation, and DOI assignment.

These repositories support FAIR principles and provide standardised metadata and access control options, including the possibility to restrict access to sensitive

data. The choice of repositories is based on their compatibility with the project's data types and dissemination strategy. Formal arrangements will be followed in accordance with institutional guidelines and repository procedures at the time of data deposit.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be accessed using widely available software tools. Textual and document data (TXT, DOCX, PDF) can be opened with standard text editors and document readers (e.g. Microsoft Word, PDF readers). Structured datasets (CSV, XLSX) can be accessed using spreadsheet software such as Microsoft Excel or equivalent open-source tools. Qualitative analysis data may be processed using NVivo or similar qualitative data analysis software. Audio files (MP3) can be accessed using standard media players.

No specialised or proprietary software is required to access the main datasets, and where specific tools are used (e.g. NVivo), exported formats will be provided to ensure broader accessibility.

Microsoft Word; Microsoft Excel; NVivo; PDF readers; audio media players -
<https://www.microsoft.com>; <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data will be provided in widely used and interoperable formats (e.g. CSV, XLSX, TXT, PDF), which allow access by different software applications and enable recombination with other datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license is chosen to enable the widest possible reuse of the data. It allows others to copy, distribute, and build upon the data, including for commercial purposes, provided that appropriate credit is given to the original author. This approach supports open science principles and maximises the visibility, accessibility, and impact of the research results.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Aggregated and anonymised datasets, as well as structured outputs such as comparative analyses and decision-support tool (DST) components, will be reusable by third parties after the end of the project. Sensitive data will remain restricted in accordance with ethical and legal requirements.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-04-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data quality will be ensured through established research methods, including structured data collection procedures, careful stakeholder selection, systematic

coding and analysis (e.g. using NVivo), and validation of results through comparison and stakeholder feedback. These processes ensure the reliability, consistency, and transparency of the data.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Leila Neimane (orcid: [0000-0002-7905-0208](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7905-0208))

The postdoctoral researcher is responsible for all main data management tasks, including data collection, organisation, documentation, analysis, and storage. This includes conducting interviews, preparing and processing datasets, and ensuring data quality and consistency.

The host institution (University of Latvia) provides the necessary infrastructure for secure data storage and backup. Where applicable, collaboration partners contribute to specific aspects of data collection and validation (e.g. stakeholder engagement and feedback). Data sharing and dissemination will be managed by the postdoctoral researcher in accordance with ethical and legal requirements.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The costs related to making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) will be covered within the project budget and supported by the infrastructure of the University of Latvia. The selected repositories (e.g. DataverseLV and Zenodo) provide data deposition and long-term access without significant additional costs. Therefore, no substantial extra funding is required beyond standard project resources.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Hash functions
- Physical access control
- Other

Data anonymisation/pseudonymisation and GDPR-compliant data handling

Data security will be ensured through a combination of technical and organisational measures. Sensitive data, such as interview recordings and transcripts, will be stored in encrypted and password-protected files on secure servers provided by the University of Latvia. Access will be restricted to the authorised researcher only.

Institutional IT infrastructure, including firewalls and controlled network environments, will be used to protect data from unauthorised external access. Physical access to devices and storage locations will be limited through institutional access control systems.

Personal and sensitive data will be anonymised or pseudonymised at an early stage of processing, and all data handling will comply with GDPR requirements. Regular backups will be performed using institutional systems to prevent data loss.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The project involves the collection and processing of qualitative data through interviews with stakeholders, which may include personal data and potentially sensitive information related to professional activities and business practices.

Legal aspects: Data collection and processing will comply with applicable data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data will be minimised and anonymised or pseudonymised where appropriate, and securely stored.

Ethical aspects: Participation in interviews will be voluntary and based on informed consent. Participants will be informed about the purpose of the research, data use, and their rights, including the right to withdraw. Confidentiality will be ensured, and sensitive data will not be publicly shared. An application for ethical review will be submitted to the Ethics Committee for Humanities and Social Sciences Research of the University of Latvia, and the project will be conducted in accordance with the committee's approval and recommendations.

These measures ensure that ethical standards are maintained and that risks related to data collection and sharing are appropriately managed.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- National laws
- Pseudonymization

Personal data will be processed in accordance with data protection regulations and ethical standards. During data collection, informed consent will be obtained from all participants, clearly specifying the purpose of the research, data use, and storage conditions.

During processing, data will be pseudonymised by replacing identifying information with codes, allowing analysis without direct identification of participants. At later stages, data will be anonymised by removing all identifiable elements before any sharing or publication.

Access to personal and sensitive data will be restricted to the authorised researcher and stored in secure, password-protected and encrypted environments. Only aggregated and fully anonymised data will be made publicly available, while access to more detailed data may be granted upon request, subject to ethical and legal requirements.

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